

Quinazolones. Part VI. Synthesis of Some Pyrrolo (1, 2-a) -Quinazolin-5 (4H)-Ones

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Pyrrolo(1,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-ones have been prepared by the cyclisation of intermediates formed from the reaction of 2-bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones with active methylene compounds.

Our interest¹ in 2-bromomethyl-4-quinazolones and the initial success in extending it to suitable derivatives which could be transformed into imidazoquinazolones led us to evolve a new route to the synthesis of pyrrolo(1,2-a)-quinazolin-5(4H)-ones, which is quite different from those reported in the literature^{2,3}.

Our approach to this synthesis is an adaptation of the procedure for the preparation of indolizines⁴ by the cyclisation of intermediates formed from the reaction of 2-bromomethylpyridine with active methylene compounds and therefore 2-bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I)¹, which was at our hand was considered to be the starting material of choice. The phenyl substituent at N₍₃₎ was considered to serve as a blocking group during cyclisation of the intermediates II, III and IV formed from the reaction with the active methylene compounds, leading to the exclusive formation of pyrrolo(1,2-a) and not (2,1-b) or their mixture as observed during the cyclisation of 1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-2-quinazolinylpropionic acid (V)².

2-bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I) when treated with sodio derivatives of acetyl acetone, diethyl malonate and ethyl acetoacetate gave the respective intermediate compounds 3-phenyl-2(2',2'-diacetylethyl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV), 3-phenyl-2(2',2'-diethoxycarbonylethyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (II) and 3-phenyl-2-(2'-acetyl-2'-ethoxycarbonylethyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) which did not cyclise to the desired pyrroloquinazolones when refluxed with acetic anhydride as adopted by Hurst *et al.*⁴ for the preparation of indolizines. However the cyclodehydration was effected as described below: Replacement of acetic anhydride with polyphosphoric acid converted II to ethyl-2H,4H-4-phenylpyrrolo(1,2-a)-quinazolin-1,5-dione-2-carboxylate (XI) but IV as expected did not give IX, rather cyclisation with simultaneous deacetylation took place to afford 1-methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo(1,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (VIII), the identity of which was established by its elemental analysis as well as its direct synthesis from 3-phenyl-2-(2'-acetylethyl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) formed by the hydrolysis of IV. The cyclodehydration by refluxing was affected with 40% alcoholic potassium hydroxide and subsequent treatment with polyphosphoric acid. However, neither acetic anhydride nor polyphosphoric could affect the cyclodehydration of III and rather intractable products were obtained. But when III

1. B. D. Singh and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 21.
2. S. C. Bell and P. H. L. Wei, *J. Heterocyclic chem.*, 1968, **5**, 179.
3. S. C. Bell and P. H. L. Wei, *ibid.*, 1968, **5**, 185.
4. J. Hurst, T. Melton and D. J. Wibberley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2948.

was refluxed with 2(*N*) sulphuric acid it could be easily cyclised into ethyl-1-methyl-4-phenyl-pyrrolo(1,2-*a*)quinazolin-5(4*H*)-one-2-carboxylate (VII) and not to X as would be expected with acetic anhydride, the identity of which was established by elemental analysis and i.r.

XI

spectra. The formation of different products with different acid catalysts indicates the role of the acid catalyst during cyclodehydration to be very important. The scheme adopted for the synthesis and a plausible mechanism for the cyclodehydration is as follows :

The reaction can be regarded as commencing with an intramolecular nucleophilic attack of the ring nitrogen atom on the side chain carbonyl group. Of the several possible routes from the enolic betaine (B) to the pyrrolo(1,2-a)quinazolin (D) the indicated route *via* the 1-protonated pyrroloquinazolinium cation (C) presumes an initial acid catalysed dehydration.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the m.ps were determined in open capillaries in H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. PPA used was of laboratory reagent grade. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

3-Phenyl-2-(2',2'-diethoxycarbonylethyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (II) : Na (0.5 g.) in dry MeOH (20 ml.) was treated with freshly distilled diethyl malonate (1.6 ml.) and to a stirred solution of which was added dropwise I (3.15 g.) in dry THF (35 ml.). After the addition was over, the reaction mixture was stirred for a further period of 1 hr. and kept overnight. It was then diluted with water, cooled, extracted with ether (15 ml. × 3), and the ethereal extract dried over Na₂SO₄. Ether was distilled off and the residual solid crystallised from benzene to afford II as colourless rectangular plates (2.5 g.; 63%), m.p. 147–148°. (Found : C, 66.8; H, 5.4; N, 7.3. C₂₂H₂₂N₂O₅ requires : C, 67.0; H, 5.6; N, 7.1%).

3-Phenyl-2-(2'-acetyl-2'-ethoxycarbonylethyl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) : To a solution of Na (0.25 g.) in dry MeOH (20 ml.) was added freshly distilled acetoacetic ester (1.3 ml.). The resulting stirred solution was treated dropwise with I (3.15 g.) in hot dry THF (35 ml.) and worked up as in the previous case to give a solid which was crystallised from benzene to yield III as colourless needles (2.4 g.; 65.9%), m.p. 168–169°. IR (KBr) 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O, keto), 1705 cm⁻¹ (C=O, ester). (Found : C, 69.3; H, 5.6; N, 7.9. C₂₁H₂₀N₂O₄ requires : C, 69.2; H, 5.5; N, 7.7%).

3-Phenyl-2-(2'-2'-diacetylethyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV) : I (3.15 g.) in dry THF (35 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring to a mixture of Na (0.25 g.) in dry MeOH (20 ml.) treated with acetyl acetone (1 ml.) and worked up as in the previous case and the resulting solid crystallised from benzene to give IV as colourless needles (2.1 g.; 62.8%), m.p. 129–125°. (Found : C, 72.0; H, 5.0; N, 8.6. C₂₀H₁₈N₂O₃ requires : C, 71.9; H, 5.3; N, 8.4%).

3-Phenyl-2-(2'-acetylethyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) : IV (1 g.) was dissolved in alcoholic KOH (40%, 20 ml.) and kept overnight. It was diluted with ice water (20 ml.), acidified with AcOH and kept in the refrigerator for 2 days when a colourless crystalline solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with ice water and crystallised from MeOH to give VI as colourless felted needles (0.5; 56.3%), m.p. 153–155°. (Found : C, 73.8; H, 5.4; N, 9.4. C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₂ requires : C, 74.0; H, 5.5; N, 9.6%).

Its, 2,4-D.N.P. derivative on crystallisation from EtOH gave red needles, m.p. 250° (decomp.).

Ethyl-2H, 4H-4-phenylpyrrolo(1,2-a)quinazolin-1,5-dione-2-carboxylate (XI) : A mixture of II (1 g.) and PPA (20 g.) was heated in oil bath at 130–135° for 1 hr. The solution diluted with water, cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over Na₂SO₄, ether evaporated and the residual solid crystallised from MeOH to furnish XI as colourless

needles (0.4 g.; 45%), m.p. 214–215°. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 4.4; N, 7.8. $C_{20}H_{16}N_2O_4$ requires: C, 69.0; H, 4.6; N, 8.0%).

Ethyl-1-methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo(1,2-a)-quinazolin-5(4H)-one-2-carboxylate (VII) : III (2 g.) in 2N H_2SO_4 (25 ml.) was refluxed for 3 hr. and the resulting reaction mixture was kept in the refrigerator overnight when a white solid separated out. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised from benzene to yield VII as felted needles (1 g.; 52.6%), m.p. 224°. IR(KBr) 1625, 1675 cm^{-1} (C = O, keto); 1720 cm^{-1} (carbonyl ester). (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.0; N, 9.1. $C_{21}H_{18}N_2O_3$ requires: C, 72.9; H, 5.2; N, 8.9%).

1-Methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo(1,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (VIII) : (i) IV (1 g.) was thoroughly mixed in PPA (20 g.) and heated in oil bath at 125–130° for 1 hr. It was diluted with water, cooled, the solid that separated was filtered, washed successfully with water, dilute NaOH and crystallised from AcOEt to give VIII as pale yellow needles (0.6 g.; 73.1%), m.p. 192°. (Found: C, 79.2; H, 5.10; N, 10.0. $C_{18}H_{14}N_2O$ requires: C, 78.9; H, 5.1; N, 10.2%).

(ii) VI (0.5 g.) in PPA (10 g.) was thoroughly mixed, heated in oil bath at 130–140° for 1 hr., diluted with water and cooled when a solid separated out. It was filtered, washed successively with water and dilute NH_3 and crystallised from AcOEt to give VIII as pale yellow needles (0.3 g.; 65%), m.p. and m.m.p. 192°.

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